

ADVANTAGES OF APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES TO PRACTICAL COURSES OF "MICROPROCESSOR SYSTEMS"

Abaskhanova Khalima Yunusovna
Tashkent University of Information Technologies
named after Muhammad al- Khwarizmi
E-mail: halimaabasxanova@gmail.com

Abstract: *The article presents the possibilities of designing microprocessor systems based on EWB software, creating diagrams, studying equipment and hardware, studying the theory of logical design of digital circuits, synthesis, modeling and research of combined and sequential types of digital devices.*

Keywords: *EWB software, digital devices, microprocessor, systems, circuits, equipment, digital circuit, logic, combinations, synthesis, simulation.*

In order to improve the education system based on advanced foreign experiences, to train qualified and competitive personnel for the labor market through the introduction of primary, secondary and secondary special professional education stages, and to attract employers to this process: from the 2020/2021 academic year, the International Standard Classifier of Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as the International Classifier) to establish a new system of primary, secondary and secondary special professional education and a network of educational institutions where differentiated educational programs will be introduced. In order to ensure the implementation of the Decree No. PF-5812 of September 6, 2019 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to improve the system of professional education", the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated August 7, 2020 466 established continuous primary, secondary and secondary special professional education in the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as professional education) determines the order of organization and implementation. Professional education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is intended for the education of individuals based on the prospects and priorities of the economy, modern techniques and technological trends, the real need for personnel in the labor market, the proposals of employers and the principle of "Learning throughout life". In the conditions of the introduction of new technologies, it can be said that the research of issues such as the application of the components of the installation of technology processes, the creation of a network based on modern technologies is urgent for experts.

One of the most important tasks solved in the educational process is the task of training specialists who have the required qualifications, who have not only theoretical knowledge, but also can apply this knowledge in solving practical problems. The current level of science and technology development requires graduates of higher education institutions to have deep theoretical knowledge and stable practical skills. In such conditions, the problem of increasing the educational activity of students of educational institutions becomes especially urgent. In order to form stable skills for solving practical problems and in-depth mastering of theoretical material, it is possible to activate the study of specific subjects of individual subjects in laboratory sessions by using modern mathematical packages that allow real-time analysis and synthesis. .Such software products include Electronics Workbench.

The extensive possibilities for simulating the operation of discrete devices provided by the Electronics Workbench software and simulation environment allow it to spread in the field of

technical education. It provides the user with a wide range of tools to implement practical ideas for the synthesis and analysis of not only discrete but also discrete devices on a computer. The ability to get a functional model of the device on the computer screen in a short time, to independently check the correctness of its operation based on a pre-prepared table or graphic model, makes the Electronics Workbench set an effective educational tool for solving practical problems. At the same time, the student communicates with the computing environment at the level of concepts, ideas, general approaches and can independently review many examples in a short time. These features of communication with the environment are especially important for the development of creative, critical and independent thinking, because the student can comprehensively study new objects, distinguish general laws and formulate generalizing statements based on his observations. The subject "Microprocessor systems" requires students to be sufficiently fluent in the methods of synthesizing and analyzing the operation of hardware devices. It is related to the complexity and variety of objects and the mathematical models for their formal representation. Limitations and assumptions that exist in the science of "Microprocessor systems" when examining the objects of study often prevent students from understanding the nature of the process taking place.

A discrete automaton is a device designed to transform discrete data. It is a directed (m, n) pole and can have k elements that perform feedback functions and are memory elements. The change in the internal state of the machine is detected by a special device - synchronous. In this case, adjacent moments of time are separated by equal intervals. Such automata are called synchronous. Asynchronous machines - moments of transition from one state to another are not predetermined. Transitions can be messy. Abstract time accepts whole and unsigned numbers $0, 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $t - 1, t, t + 1, t + 2, \dots$ (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Abstract time

An illustrative method of setting up a discrete automaton with memory is the use of timing diagrams that show the order of formation of output signals for a given sequence of input signals. In addition, the operation of the automaton can be described by a transition graph, i.e. a directed connected graph, each of its vertices corresponds to one of the internal states, and each of the edges between the vertices represents a transition of the automaton from one internal state to another. Input states are recorded near the edge and cause state-to-state transitions.

Figure 2. A panel of logical elements

The Electronics Workbench application is a software development and simulation tool for electrical circuits.

The user interface consists of a menu bar, a toolbar, and a workspace.

Figure 3. The workspace of Electronics Workbench.

It should be noted the high impact of the software package developed on the basis of EWB, the development of the student's creative ability: through trial and error, he will gain new experience, reach a new level. Based on the above, when students are learning science, computer circuit modeling systems are adequately and effectively included in educational programs, ensuring complete organization of educational activities and their correct use in the educational process.

The list of used literature

1. Abasxanova, X. Yu. "Textbook for college students majoring in" digital technology" 5.55. 01.01-" Telecommunication technologies" Tashkent." (2021).
2. Abaskhanova, X. Yu, and I. N. Juraev. "Khoshimova FR Textbook for college students majoring in" digital technology" 5.55. 01.01-" Telecommunication technologies". Tashkent." (2021).
3. Abaskhanova, H. Yu, and K. Sherjanova. "Creating microprocessor systems for people with disabilities creating microprocessor systems for people with disabilities. Collection of

reports of the republican scientific-practical conference" prospects for the development of information and communication technologies." Karshi-2018." 87-89.

4. Abaskhanova, H. Y. "Applying infocommunication technologies to agriculture." Current problems of modern science. Xalqaro konferentsiya. Chicago USA-2022.-6.

5. Yu, Abaskhanova Kh. "Analysis of information and communication technologies in green environment monitoring." International conference on information science and communications technologies applications, trends and opportunities: ICISCT. 2022.

6. Yu, Abaskhanova KH. "Features of introduction of innovative technologies in agriculture of Uzbekistan." International scientific journal "Universum: Technical science (2021).

7. Yu, Abaskhanova Kh. "Advantages of using digital technologies in agriculture." Agro science. Agrarian-economic, scientific-practical magazine. Tashkent-2022.3-appendix (81)-no.-pages104-105.

8. Abaskhanova K. Y. ORGANIZING THE CLASSES OF MICROCONTROLLER SYSTEMS AT SCHOOLS. – 2023.

9. Abaskhanova K. Y. USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF PROGRAMMABLE DIGITAL DEVICES. – 2023.

10. Abasxanova, X. Yu. "Modeling digital devices with the help of vhdl programming language. Current problems of modern science." International conference. Chicago USA. 2022.

11. Halima A. APPLICATION OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES FOR REMOTE MONITORING OF GREENHOUSE LAND PLOTS //Universum: технические науки. – 2023. – №. 1-4 (106). – С. 31-33.

12. Xalima A. EFFICIENCY OF APPLYING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES TO THE PLANT DEVELOPMENT //Universum: технические науки. – 2023. – №. 7-4 (112). – С. 33-35.